

THE WAYS TO AMELIORATE ORAL PRODUCTIVE SKILL RESORTING TO ELEMENTS OF AFFECTIVE FACTORS

UDK: И 37.02

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Annotation: In language learning process improving oral productive skill require not only utilizing language devices, but also it is vital to take into account the intrinsic factors of learners. Provided article is intended to address to elements of affective factors pointing out their role in enhancing oral productive skills. Additionally, the ways to uplift speaking through elements of affective factors are presented in the article.

Keywords: oral productive skill, elements of affective factors, self-esteem, anxiety, motivation, risk-taking, extraversion, students' personality.

Productive activities include speaking and writing. That is, when a person actively produces speech orally or in writing. Accordingly, with the help of the speech apparatus or motor skills, information is generated in the form of an oral or written source [1]. Productions skills imply the skills that require learner to be creative and well-rounded enough to express notions whether in oral or written form. Unlike receptive skills, these ones are much sophisticated, because aside from absorbing information it is critical to deliver the message as clearly as possible. Speaking is the pronunciation of sounds that make up words, sentences and fully formed speech that carries certain information. The process of development and formation of speaking goes through several stages - from simple sounds, through words and phrases, to complexly constructed sentences. In order to bring ordinary speaking to the state of so-called "eloquence", it is necessary to constantly improve the skill. The breadth of horizons allows you to talk on

different topics. Information is drawn from various sources - newspapers, magazines, books, electronic sources. Speaking as a type of productive type of speech activity. Goals, objectives and content of teaching speaking a foreign language

Speaking in modern Exemplary Foreign Language Programs occupies an important place. Today, the goal in the field of foreign languages is to create conditions for personal formation and personal development with the help of the language being studied. Currently, training in the system in the process of teaching a language as a means of communication and knowledge of another culture and awareness of one's linguistic and cultural origins is relevant [2]. This goal is realized through: firstly, the education of the student by means of the subject "foreign language" of socially significant qualities and personal characteristics; secondly, expanding his individual picture of the world by introducing native speakers of the language being studied to the linguistic and conceptual pictures of the world; thirdly, introducing him to a different language system, getting to know a different system of values and better understanding of his "origins" and "roots", commonality with "alien" and difference from "other"; fourthly, mastering subject knowledge, language and speech skills, communication skills and methods of cognitive activity in the studied non-native language and with the help of this language. The components of this subsystem, being hierarchically dependent on each other, are combined into four interconnected blocks, namely: units of language and speech; topics, problems, subjects of speech; speech actions; feelings and emotions.

Based on questionnaire conducted in the group of 20 freshman students, it has revealed that positive affective factors dominated over negative ones. Levels of self-esteem, extraversion and self-confidence of freshmen students were fairly adequate and accounted for 20% and 12 % respectively. Anxiety while speaking activities occurred only in times when students tried to deliver and explain sophisticated things and this section constituted to under 15%. When it comes to motivation, students were fairly engaged in discussion as the topic was appealing

to them (Dysfunctional family and its impact on teenagers adjustment) and this affective factor accounted for in the vicinity 15%. The highest percentage were revealed to be risk-taking factor(30%), regardless mistakes and fear relatively many students tried to be involved in activity, getting out from their comfort zone.

In developing oral productive skill, it is critical to pay attention to student's emotions. According to Goetz et al. (2003), there are three reasons for exploring emotions in education: their impact on learning quality, students' well-being (physical and mental state) and their role in socialization (peers and teachers) [3]. According to Brown (2007), these factors are specified by the individual students like motivation, attitude, personal practice and study habits. Each of these factors is an individual element of learners' ability to acquire a foreign language but each component also interacts with another [4].

Here are the ways to uplift speaking through elements of affective factors:

1. Identifying students' personality The initial step helps to cooperate with student effectively, accordingly it serves as a gateway to apply the appropriate techniques further.
2. Practice ways to maintain a positive attitude. It is vital not to underestimate the role of attitude in classroom, negative mindset easily infects students and may cause discouragement and tension, altogether much of stress leads to much serious problems such as FLA (stands for foreign language anxiety) [5].

3. Praise and then rectify. While student's oral performance, it is advisable to find both strong and weak sides of speech performance. This technique facilitates to correct the students' mistakes without impacting on self-esteem and motivation.
4. Permit to resort to code-switching only in complex topics. Code-switching in moderate is helpful, because it let the students to express their notions regardless some hindrances, however make sure this compensatory method is used only in sophisticated topics. Code-switching was deemed to be as a useful strategy that assisted the learners convey their ideas to be fully understood and meaningful in the interaction process [6].

Personality is everything characteristics which can affect characteristic especially the way of thinking, feeling even behaving of someone. Aside from language devices, there are factors stemming from students' inner state, which critically influence on progress in target language. These factors are specified by the individual students like motivation, attitude, personal practice and study habits. Each of these factors is an individual element of learners' ability to acquire a foreign language but each component also interacts with another. Learning a different language is very challenging but if the learner has internal desire to learn any language, he/she can do well. It is an internal or external desire in people, which increases learners' interest to learn a different language to achieve a goal.

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UZLUKSIZ TA’LIM TIZIMIDA INGLIZ TILINI O’RGATISH MASALALARI

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada dunyoda tan olingan rasmiy tillar, asosan, ingliz tilining ommalashib borish sabablari, bu tilni o’rganish va o’rgatish jarayonida qo’llanilayotgan zamonaviy pedagogik usullar haqida so’z boradi.

Kalit so’zlar: Rasmiy tillar, xorijiy tillar, ingliz, rus, arab, fransuz, ispan va xitoy tillari, zamonaviy pedagogik va axborot kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari;

Til bu mamlakatlarni bir biri bilan bog’lovchi ko’prik demakdir. Hozirgi kunda jahon muloqotida tillarni bilish darajasi muhim rol o’ynab, turli xalqlar bilan